

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON OLFACTORY DELIVERY OF HERBAL BIOACTIVES: SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO FORMULATE HERBAL ANTI-STRESS INHALER

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ABSTRACT

The review highlights the strong potential of olfactory delivery for administering herbal bioactives, a potential route characterised by its rapid onset of action and broad patient acceptability. This therapeutic relevance is primarily linked to the direct connection between the olfactory system and the limbic system; a vital brain region is responsible for modulating emotional regulation and stress responses. The paper demonstrates recent scientific evidence on how aromatic phytochemicals, mainly terpenoids and phenolic compounds present in essential oils, interact with olfactory receptors to effectively influence neural pathways involved with stress, anxiety, and mood regulation. It also identified Primary herbal selection used in anti-stress inhalers is determined, as well as the essential analytical techniques required for profiling these volatile constituents are to ensure quality control. Along with

the review focuses on various formulation approaches, including essential oil blends, nano-emulsions, nasal aromatherapy sticks, and solid-inhaler systems, emphasis is placed on optimising key aspects such as the stability, safety, and efficiency of volatile release. By carefully selecting the appropriate ingredients, adjusting concentration, and delivery mechanism. This review also highlighted the anxiolytic and stress-reducing effects resulting from olfactory exposure, thereby consolidating advancements in phytochemistry, delivery systems, and neuroscientific mechanisms to provide a robust scientific foundation for the rational design of optimized herbal anti-stress inhalers.

KEYWORDS: Olfactory delivery, herbal bioactive, anti-stress, aromatherapy, inhalers.

INTRODUCTION

Stress is a complex physiological and psychological condition, commonly experienced state of tension and pressure. Stress arises when individuals perceive internal or external demands as exceeding their adaptive capacity, posing a potential threat to physical and mental well-being. Represented the body's internal physical, biological, and psychological response to perceived challenges, anxiety or uncertainty.^[1] When exposure to stress is excessive or prolonged, the normal regulatory system of the body becomes disrupted, leading to cumulative physiological burden and functional imbalance.^[2] Stress is a response that occurs when a person feels that life's demands by challenging around them and their adaptive capacity.^[3] Modern psychophysiology defines stress as the activation of coordinated systems—including the brain, autonomic nervous system, endocrine system, and immune pathways—designed to maintain stability through change, a process called allostasis^[4] systems—along with the brain, autonomic nervous system, endocrine system, and immune pathways—develop to keep stability throughout change, a process called allostasis.^[4] However, chronic activation of this system results in “allostatic load,” characterised by cumulative wear and tear on the body, which contributes to hormonal dysregulation, impaired immune function, and adverse effects on mood and behaviour.^[2] Increasing academic, professional, and social pressure has made stress a widespread public health concern, prompting the search for effective and safe stress management strategies.

Herbal anti-stress inhalers, formulated using essential oils and plant-derived extracts, have gained attention as a rapid, convenient and noninvasive approach for stress reduction.^[5] Unlike synthetic anxiolytic agents, whose long-term use is often limited by tolerance, side effects, and dependency, herbal inhalation therapies offer a safer complementary alternative. The effectiveness of these inhalers depends on the careful selection of herbal bioactive essential oils, formulation stability, and optimization of aromatic profiles to ensure therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance.^[6] As a result, there is a give attention on herbal remedies, specifically those delivered through inhalation. When we inhale Herbal essential oils that provide calmness due to olfactory factory stimulation with the presence of bioactive volatile compounds that can interact with the limbic system, which is the brain's reason, they enhance calmness in times of stress and anxiety. Recent research has enhanced the importance of understanding the bioactivity therapeutic result, phytochemistry and

mechanism and formulation science of inhalable natural products to minimize therapeutic results.^[7] This systematic review demonstrates that inhalation aromatherapy shows beneficial effects in reducing stress and anxiety across various clinical settings, supporting its role as a safe and effective complementary therapy or alongside conventional treatment.^[5] The study demonstrates that olfactory stimulation from essential oils can modulate neural activity and neurotransmitter pathways associated with anxiety and stress.^[7] When essential oil blends that Aroma exposure may result in a synergistic effect, which enhances both mental and emotional outcomes.^[4] The researcher found that Inhalation of essential oils can help to reduce symptoms of anxiety, and the olfactory system plays an important role in inhalation.

ESSENTIAL OILS USED IN HERBAL ANTI-STRESS INHALERS

Essential oils are concentrated aromatic extracts from medicinal plants and have been widely explored for their therapeutic and stress-relieving property through inhalation. These oils contain volatile bioactive constituents that rapidly reach the central nervous system via the olfactory pathway, producing therapeutic effects on emotional and cognitive functions. Inhalation of essential oils allows direct interaction of aromatic molecules with olfactory receptor, which transmits signals to the limbic system, a brain region involved in stress regulation, mood, and emotional behaviour.^[7,29]

Among various essential oils, Sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) essential oil has been extensively studied for its calming and mood-enhancing effects. Clinical and experimental studies have reported that inhalation of (*Citrus sinensis*) essential oil significantly reduces anxiety level and promotes relaxation, making it a commonly used component in anti-stress formulation.^[10,13] The anxiolytic activity of citrus oil is primarily attributed to monoterpenes such as limonene, which modulate neurotransmitter pathways associated with emotional regulation.

Inhalation aromatherapy of peppermint (*mentha piperita*) improves alertness and shows impactful activity on positive mood modulation.^[12] *Ocimum sanctum* (Tulsi) is a well-recognised adaptogenic herb traditionally used to reduce anxiety and stress. Growing scientific evidences demonstrate that inhalation of essential oils enhances mental clarity and reduces anxiety through the Olfactory pathway.^[28] Rosemary (*Rosmarinus Officinalis*) essential oil has been reported to exhibit stress-reducing and cognitive-enhancing effects, with inhalation studies demonstrating that it reduces anxiety and improves mental alertness among stressed individuals.^[15,16] The review highlights how natural essential oil-based work

and active compounds, such as inhalers, reduce stress. Recent studies mainly explore stress-reducing phytoconstituents like citrus oils, peppermint, Tulsi, rosemary, and lavender how they act on the central nervous system via activating the olfactory pathway. Research shows that the Inhalation route can produce a rapid onset of action as compared to oral administration, which helps to reduce stress and anxiety. In addition, most scientific work is being done on formulation approaches, strategies, including dose-controlled devices, nasal stick inhalers, etc.

This comprehensive review focuses on the mechanisms of action, formulation approaches, therapeutic potential, quality challenges, and future possibilities of herbal anti-stress inhalers. By blending the results from pharmacognosy, aromatherapy, and pharmaceutical formulation sciences. this review is intended to emphasize the scientific basis and development strategies for creating safe and effective inhalable herbal anti-stress products.

Table 1: Major phytochemical constituents of essential oils used in herbal anti-stress inhalers.

Essential oil	Major constituents	Chemical class	Reported activity
<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Limonene	Myrcene Monoterpenes Anxiolytic,	mood elevation ^[6,10]
<i>Mentha piperita</i>	menthone Menthol	Monoterpenes	CNS Stimulation stress reduction ^[12,13]
<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i>	rosmarinic acid, Eugenol	Phenolic	anxiolytic ^[14,28]
<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Camphor, 1,8-cineol Monoterpenes	Monoterpenes	anti-stress ^[15,16]

MECHANISM OF ACTION

When herbal active compounds (e.g., essential oil terpenes) are inhaled, they activate the olfactory receptors in the nasal epithelium, promoting neuronal impulses that reach to the olfactory bulb and then extend into the limbic system, including the amygdala and hippocampus.^[7] At that point, these volatile compounds can regulate the emotional centre in the brain and modulate neurotransmitter release (including serotonin or endorphins), as a result reducing anxiety and stress. Along with this olfactory pathway, lipophilic molecules like linalool can be absorbed into via the lungs within the bloodstream, cross the blood–brain barrier, and act centrally.^[7] Experimental studies show that inhaled linalool mediates anxiolytic effects via GABA_A receptor activation, as illustrated by flumazenil antagonism in mice lacking motor impairment.^[8] The study shows that interaction between receptors in

the brain and linalool, a common monoterpenes present in many essential oils. This research shows that these inhibitory receptors, which are essential for controlling urinal excitability, can be modulated by linalool. Linalool may help lessen the neuronal hyperactivity linked to stress and anxiety by improving GABAergic signalling.^[9]

Fig. 1: Biological Effects of Essential Oils on the CNS.

In addition, linalool has been observed to bind and allosterically modulate GABA_A receptors, increasing the calming effect of GABA on neurons.^[9] Its application also decreased respiratory neuron activity in the neonatal rat brain–spinal cord sample by acting through GABA_A mechanisms.

PLANT PROFILE

Sweet orange

Fig. 2: Sweet Orange.

Synonyms: *citrus sinensis*

Biological source: It is a hybrid species likely from a cross between the pomelo and the Mandarin, and it belongs to the *citrus* genus.

Family: Rutaceae

Uses: Sweet Orange provide anti-stress benefits through its Aroma and nutritional compounds, which can help lower stress hormones and improve mood.

The study demonstrates that inhaling the aroma of *citrus sinensis* is beneficial for reducing anxiety and stress.^[10] Inhalation of the essential oil of *citrus sinensis* helps to reduce anxiety, heart rate, and pain in pregnant women.^[11]

Peppermint

Fig. 3: Peppermint.

Synonyms: *Mentha piperita l.*

Biological source: It is a cross between water mint, there is a (*Mentha Aquatica*) and (*Mentha spicata*).

Family: Lamiaceae

Chemical constituents: menthol, menthone and linalool.

Uses: **Peppermint** is valued for its anti-stress property due to its calming aroma and muscle-relaxing effect.

Inhalation of peppermint essential oil can reduce the anxiety effect in patients with acute coronary syndrome in the emergency department.^[12] Peppermint aromatherapy helps to reduce stress and anxiety and produces the calming effect of menthol by activation of the limbic system.^[13]

Tulsi

Fig. 4: Tulsi.

Synonyms: *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (syn. *Ocimum sanctum*).

Biological source: it consists a fresh dried leaves of the plant species *Ocimum* l., commonly known as *Ocimum sanctum* (also called holy basil) and *Ocimum basilicum*.

Family: Lamiaceae

Chemical constituent: Eugenol, rosmarinic acid, apigenin, and ocimumosides.

Uses: It acts as an adaptogen, helping to reduce stress.

The study shows that the supplementation with an *Ocimum tenuiflorum* extract for 8 weeks helps to reduce stress, tension and enhance sleep quality.^[14]

Rosemary

Fig. 5: Rosemary.

Synonyms: Rosmarinus Officinalis

Biological source: It is native to the Mediterranean region, but it's now cultivated worldwide. The part used includes the leaf and flowering tops, which are known for their aromatic and medicinal property due to high concentrations of essential oils at other bioactive compounds.

Family: Lamiaceae

Chemical constituents: rosmarinic acid, Carnosic acid, ursolic acid, and 1,8-cineol.

Uses: The aroma of Rosemary essential oil may reduce cortisol level, the stress hormone, and studies suggest it could improve mood and sleep quality.

Rosemary aromatherapy helps to reduce stress and anxiety and produces a calming effect in pre-hospital emergency personnel. Inhalation of Rosemary aroma is a safe, effective, and inexpensive tool that enhances calmness and reduces stress.^[15] Inhalation of Rosemary containing rosmarinic acid and diterpenes shows an effect on reducing stress and produces a calming effect, and also benefits for heart rate.^[16]

Table 2: Formulation approaches.

Formulation Aspect	Description
Delivery system	Cotton-wick nasal inhalers are extensively used for that reason; they return volatile oil and provide control of Aroma release, as recorded across clinical aromatherapy studies. ^[17,18]
Essential oil concentration	Used an undiluted essential oil inhaler for a rapid one set, even though diluted forms 5 to 20% are recommended when a gentle effect is desired. ^[19]
Aroma Blending Principles	Balancing the top, middle, and base notes helps preserve the stability of Aroma and therapeutic Synergy, especially for stress blends. ^[17]
Synergistic phytochemicals Action	Blending of monoterpenes and phenolic compounds boosts anxiolytic effect as compared to single oil inhalation, showing measurable mood benefit and calmness. ^[20]
Devices type	Reported devices, which are aroma sticks via nasal inhaler devices and design influences rate, Aroma intensity, and usability. ^[18]
Stability assessment	Citrus oils are prone to oxidation; all essential oil inhalers require air-tight, light-resistant packaging to preserve active constituents.

SAFETY, STABILITY AND STORAGE

Safety and stability aspects for essential oils are well established in the scientific and clinical literature. Essential oils must be stored in dark, airtight glass containers to avoid exposure to light, heat, and oxygen, all of which accelerate chemical degradation and induce changes in the volatile profile.^[22] Oxidation of common monoterpenes (for example, linalool and

limonene) produces hydroperoxides and other oxygenated derivative compounds that simultaneously degrade aroma and, importantly, have crucially greater potential to trigger skin sensitisation than the parent compounds.^[23] Citrus oils, which are rich in D-limonene, are highly prone to autoxidation and should be kept stored accordingly under cool, dark, oxygen-limited conditions that approach to minimise formation of allergenic oxidation products.^[23,30] For inhalation use, analysis and clinical guidance is advised recommending limiting exposure to non-irritant concentrations, avoiding direct contact with eyes and mucous membranes, and keeping inhalation devices away from children and susceptible individuals.^[24,25] Mostly, the literature supports storage in airtight, dark glass, decreasing oxygen and heat exposure, and exercising caution with inhalation to reduce both chemical degradation and risk of irritation, burning, sensation.^[23]

SUMMARY

1. Why are these herbs suitable?

Herbs	Key benefits
Sweet orange (<i>Citrus sinensis</i>)	It helps to reduce stress and promote relaxation due to limonene-rich aroma. ^[26]
Peppermint (<i>Mentha piperita</i>)	Enhance mental clarity, reduce tension, and improve alertness. ^[27]
Tulsi (<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i>)	It acts as an adaptogen, helping regulate stress response and produce calmness. ^[28]
Rosemary (<i>Rosmarinus Officinalis</i>)	Support cognitive balance and mood due to 1,8-cineole activity. ^[21]

2) Why is the inhalation route effective?

The inhalation route is widely used due to its rapid onset of action. Herbal essential oils and aromatic compounds have a direct effect on the brain and provide calmness, and also patient acceptability.

1. Rapid absorption and immediate effect

When aromatic compounds are inhaled, they are frequently absorbed through the nasal mucosa and transported directly to the brain. This provides a faster therapeutic onset in comparison with oral routes, which involve digestion and metabolism.^[29]

CONCLUSION

Herbal anti-stress inhalers, made with suitable, calming essential oils and stabilised appropriately, can be a gentle and natural way to help manage daily stress. Research or current evidence suggests that inhaled phytochemicals and natural bioactives can swiftly

influence the olfactory–limbic system, leading to improved mood, reduced stress, and enhanced mental clarity. The combination of selected herbs or their blend forms a gentle and harmonious blend that supports overall well-being, while proper formulation strategies ensure product quality, safety, and stability. Although current evidence shows that the use of herbal inhalers may help to reduce stress. Overall, well-formulated herbal inhalers provide a rapid, convenient, and non-invasive approach to stress management, integrating traditional herbal wisdom with modern scientific principles.

FUTURE PROSPECTS and OPPORTUNITIES

Investigating New Herbs

While well-known aromatic herbs like *citrus sinensis*, *Mentha piperita*, *Ocimum tenuiflorum* and *Rosmarinus Officinalis* have been extensively studied for their stress relieving and anxiolytics effects, a wide range of medicinal plants rich in volatile phytochemicals remain unexplored. Conducting systematic pharmacognostic evaluation and phytochemical analysis of these lesser-known aromatic herbs could lead to the discovery of new by active compound and ideal for anti stress inhaler formulations.^[31]

Synergistic Essential Oil Blends

The recent evidences suggest that combination of Essential oil may enhance anxiolytic effects compared to individual oils due to synergistic interaction among their phytoconstituents. Future study should aim to identify the most effective Essential oil combinations and standardization of herbal bioactive.^[32]

REFERENCE

1. Kannur DM, Kulkarni AA. Stress and its physiological impact. J Pharm Biomed, 2008; 2(3): 45–52.
2. McEwen BS. Stress, adaptation, and disease: Allostasis and allostatic load. Ann N Y Acad Sci., 1998; 840(1): 33–44.
3. Lazarus RS, Folkman S. Stress, appraisal, and coping. New York: Springer, 1984.
4. McEwen BS, Wingfield JC. What is in a name? Integrating homeostasis, allostasis and stress. Horm Behav, 2010; 57(2): 105–111.
5. Hedigan F, Sheridan H, Sasse A. Benefit of inhalation aromatherapy as a complementary treatment for stress and anxiety in a clinical setting: A systematic review. Complement Ther Clin Pract., 2023; 52: 101750.

6. Sá RCDS, Andrade LN, Sousa DP. A review on anti-inflammatory activity of monoterpenes. *Molecules*, 2013; 18(1): 1227–1254. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules18011227>
7. Cui C, Zhang Y, Li X, Wang J, Liu H. Olfactory stimulation and limbic system modulation through essential oil inhalation. *J Ethnopharmacology*, 2022; 289: 115127.
8. Harada H, Kashiwadani H, Kanmura Y, Kuwaki T. Linalool inhalation produces anxiolytic effects via GABA_A receptor modulation. *Front Behav Neurosc*, 2018; 12: 1–10.
9. Winkler C, Wirz A, Steigerwald M, Heilmann J. Interaction of linalool with GABA_A receptors. *Neuropharmacology*, 2017; 113: 128–137.
10. Mannucci C, Calapai F, Cardia L, Inferrera G, D'Arena G, Di Pietro M, Navarra M, Gangemi S, Spagnolo EV, Calapai G. Clinical Pharmacology of Citrus aurantium and Citrus sinensis for the Treatment of Anxiety. Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine: eCAM, Dec. 2, 2018; 2018: 3624094.
11. Nascimento JC, Gonçalves VS, Souza BR, de C Nascimento L, de Carvalho BM, Nogueira PC, Santos JP, Borges LP, Goes TC, de Souza JB, Coutinho HD. Effectiveness of aromatherapy with sweet orange oil (*Citrus sinensis* L.) in relieving pain and anxiety during labor. *Explore (New York, NY)*, 21(1): 103081.
12. Soleimani M, Kashfi LS. The effect of aromatherapy with peppermint essential oil on anxiety of cardiac patients in emergency department: A placebo-controlled study. *Complementary Therapies in Clinical Practice*, 2022; 46: 101533.
13. Qorahman WMM, Fatmawati ZI, Steven R. The effect of Benson relaxation and peppermint aromatherapy on emotional mental disorders in hypertension patients. *Indonesian Journal of Global Health Research*, 2024; 6(6): 1091–1100.
14. Lopresti AL, Smith SJ, Metse AP, Drummond PD. A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial investigating the effects of an *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (Holy Basil) extract (HolixerTM) on stress, mood, and sleep in adults experiencing stress. *Frontiers in nutrition*, Sep. 2, 2022; 9: 965130.
15. Rahimi H, Nakhaei M, Mehrpooya N, Hatami SM, Vagharseyyedin SA. The Effect of Inhaling the Aroma of Rosemary Essential Oil on the Pre-Hospital Emergency Personnel Stress and Anxiety: A Quasi-Experimental Study. *Modern Care Journal*, 16(3).
16. Kuwata H, Ookoshi K, Shimazu K, Fukumitsu S, Aida K. Safety and stress-reducing effects of rosemary extract: an open-label trial and randomized double-blind crossover study. *Journal of Clinical Biochemistry and Nutrition*, Sep. 10, 2025; 77(3): 280.

17. Buckle J. Clinical aromatherapy: essential oils in healthcare. 3rd ed. London: Elsevier, 2015.
18. Tisserand R, Young R. Essential oil safety: a guide for health care professionals. 2nd ed. London: Churchill Livingstone, 2014.
19. Lis-Balchin M. Aromatherapy science: a guide for healthcare professionals. London: Pharmaceutical Press, 2006.
20. Moss M, Oliver L. Synergistic effects of essential oil blends on cognition and mood. *J Funct Foods*, 2014; 8: 67–75.
21. Moss M, Oliver L. Aromas and mood regulation. *Chem Senses*, 2012; 37(2): 139–45.
22. Burfield T. Safety of essential oils: a review. *Int J Aromather*, 2000; 10(3–4): 101–18.
23. de Groot AC. Limonene hydroperoxides: identification, characterization and clinical relevance. *Dermatitis*, 2019; 30(2): 75–86.
24. Vora J. Safety guidance for aromatherapy and inhalation of essential oils: a clinical perspective. *J Integr Complement Med.*, 2024; 30(1): 12–22.
25. Caballero-Gallardo K, Olivero-Verbel J. Essential oils as therapeutic agents: safety considerations for inhalation delivery. *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol*, 2023; 93: 103910.
26. Goes TC, Antunes FD, Alves PB, Teixeira-Silva F. Effect of *Citrus sinensis* essential oil on anxiety. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.*, 2012; 2012: 1–5.
27. Moss M, Howrah R, Wilkinson L, Webb C. Influence of peppermint aroma on performance and mood. *Int J Neurosci*, 2010; 120(1): 15–20.
28. Cohen MM. Tulsi (*ocimum sanctum*): traditional uses and modern research. *J Ayurveda Integr Med.*, 2014; 5(4): 251–9.
29. Herz RS. Aromatherapy facts and fictions: the olfactory-limbic connection. *Int J Neurosci*, 2009; 119(2): 263–77.
30. Kharab RM. Stability of essential oils under various storage conditions. *Phytother Res.*, 2001; 15(8): 581–4.
31. Edris AE. Pharmaceutical and therapeutic potentials of essential oils and their individual volatile constituents: A review. *Phytother Res.*, 2007; 21(4): 308–323. doi:10.1002/ptr.2072.
32. Moss M, Oliver L. Plasma 1,8-cineole correlates with cognitive performance following exposure to rosemary essential oil aroma. *Ther Adv Psychopharmacol*, 2012; 2(3): 103–113. doi:10.1177/2045125312436575.